

Determination of the Location of Partial Discharges in the Power Transformer Model Using UHF Sensors

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SUMMARY

Power transformers are essential components of power generation plants, transmission systems and large industrial plants. Any malfunction of the power transformer would reduce the reliability of the power system. The reliable operation of power transformers is important for the safety of the supply of electricity to consumers and mainly depends on the state of the electrical insulation of the power transformer. Therefore, all types of internal insulation damage in the power transformer should be determined as soon as possible. Partial discharges (PDs) are a reliable indicator of the condition of the electrical insulation. Partial discharges caused by initial weaknesses in the insulation system of the power transformer cannot be completely ignored, because they can warn in advance of possible serious deficiencies, which in the worst cases could cause irreversible failure of the power transformer. In general, partial discharge can occur at voltages higher than 5 kV.

Using simulations in Ansys HFSS (High Frequency Structure Simulator) and three different models of power transformer construction from simple to the most complex one, this paper investigates waveforms and delays of ultra-high frequency (UHF) PD electromagnetic signals at four UHF sensors mounted at different locations of a small power transformer tank of core construction. Then location of PD source was determined. Full-wave electromagnetic simulations are performed on the model of a small power transformer of core construction. Electromagnetic waves are emitted and received by dipole antennas as source of partial discharges in the insulation of the power transformer and UHF sensors.

The active parts of the power transformer can influence the shape and size of the received signals on UHF sensors, the source of which is a partial discharge in the electrical insulation of the power transformer. At the same time, the attenuation and distortion of the signal on the receiving UHF antenna is all the greater if the path of the partial discharge signal is more distorted in relation to the straight line that connects the source of the partial discharges and the corresponding UHF sensor.

All reflections of electromagnetic UHF PD waves from the walls of the tank, three-phase magnetic core and three-phase primary and secondary windings are taken into account. All diffractions of UHF PD waves around active metal parts and through narrow apertures of winding coils and disks of transformer are included. The simulation is based on finite element method. It is a numerical method that is applied to differential equations with limit values in order to obtain an approximate solution. The underlying problem is defined here as high-frequency problem, as opposed to a quasi-static problem or a low-frequency problem. Advantages and disadvantages of this computer simulation will be described.

KEYWORDS

Partial Discharge (PD) – Power Transformer – Signal propagation – Source location – UHF sensor – Ansys HFSS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Finding the location of partial discharges (PDs) in a simplified power transformer model using two, three or four ultra-high frequency (UHF) transmitters, using simulations in MATLAB, with some basic assumptions (i.e. suitable delayed limit PD waveforms, appropriate mineral oil dielectric permittivity, and average signal attenuation in the oil) is presented in [1]. In [2], simulations of UHF partial discharge signal propagation using finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) modelling were carried out using the XFDTD 7.0 software, taking into account transformer tank, cylindrical or cuboid obstacle. In [3], a computational model of the power transformer was built in CST Microwave Studio and was used to evaluate attenuations of PD signals and, on the basis of them, find optimal UHF sensors positions. .NET Windows Presentation Foundation (.NET WPF) and Helix 3D were used to model the transformer structure with simplified obstacles in [4]. In [5], results of attenuations of UHF PD signals in 3-D computational model of oil-filled transformer tank with winding and results gained from appropriate experimental setup were compared. In [6], PD Location in Power Transformers was carried out on experimental configuration with two different obstacles, one of the core and the second of the winding. Two sensor diamond-shaped arrays were used with four UHF sensors each. FDTD technique was used to simulate propagation of UHF PD signals in simplified model consisting of conductive transformer tank with mineral oil in [7]. In [8], it was resulted that PD pulses with steeper front time cause to smaller energy and peak values of the acquired UHF signals. In [9], four electric field probes and binary particle swarm optimization method were used in PD source location in a power transformer model using finite integration technique (FIT) in simulation software CST Microwave Studio. In MATLAB, the non-iterative method was executed for PD location using the time difference of arrival of the UHF signals and the coordinates of the UHF sensors in [10]. It had been observed in [11] that the sensor location had no significant effect on the observed UHF PD waveforms on electric field sensors. In [12], the simulation results show that the sensors will receive a stronger signal when the distance to the PD source is reduced and the amplitude of the EM wave is drastically weakened after diffraction on the windings and core.

Using simulations in Ansys HFSS and three different models of power transformer construction from simple to the most complex one, this paper investigates waveforms and delays of UHF PD electromagnetic signals at four UHF sensors mounted at different locations of a small power transformer tank of core construction. Then location of PD source was determined. Full-wave electromagnetic simulations are performed on the model of a small power transformer of core construction. Electromagnetic waves are emitted and received by dipole antennas as source of partial discharges in the insulation of the power transformer and UHF sensors, respectively.

All reflections of electromagnetic UHF PD waves from the walls of the tank, three-phase magnetic core and three-phase primary and secondary windings are taken into account. All diffractions of UHF PD waves around active metal parts and through narrow apertures of winding coils and disks of transformer are included. The simulation is based on finite element method. It is a numerical method that is applied to differential equations with limit values in order to obtain an approximate solution. The underlying problem is defined here as high-frequency problem, as opposed to a quasi-static problem or a low-frequency problem. Other features, i.e., advantages and disadvantages of this computer simulation will be described.

2. INFLUENCES ON UHF PD WAVE PROPAGATION IN POWER TRANSFORMER

Power apparatus is generally in the form of metal-shielded equipment. Released energies from partial discharges, such as light, heat and electromagnetic waves, are prevented from passing through the metal case, so they must be detected by a suitable sensor inside the case.

The recorded signal on the UHF sensor is affected by the following [1]:

- Special type, strength and position of the source of partial discharges;
- Frequency response, installation location, sensitivity and UHF sensor radiation emission and reception diagram;
- Appropriate propagation path of UHF waves between the source of partial discharges and the UHF sensor, which is usually determined by the internal structure of the power transformer;
- Sensitivity of the measuring device.

The power transformer is made of different materials that can be:

- 1) dielectric (e.g., mineral oil, oil-paper insulation, pressboard);
- 2) electrically conductive (e.g., copper);
- 3) soft magnetic (e.g., electrical steel).

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The active parts of the power transformer can influence the shape and size of the received signals on UHF sensors, the source of which is a partial discharge in the electrical insulation of the power transformer. At the same time, the attenuation and distortion of the signal on the receiving UHF antenna is all the greater if the path of the partial discharge signal is more distorted in relation to the straight line that connects the source of the partial discharges and the corresponding UHF sensor.

Signal attenuation originates from the loss of signal energy when bouncing off the metal tank and metal active parts of the transformer core and the high and low voltage windings. Whenever it encounters any metal obstacle, part of the signal will be reflected and the remaining part will continue to propagate by diffraction (bending) the wave around the obstacle.

If, in the simulation in this work, the oil-paper insulation of the high and low voltage windings and the intermediate insulation from the pressboard were taken into account instead of mineral oil, additional attenuation and refraction would occur at the boundaries: oil-(oil-paper insulation) and (oil-paper insulation)-oil or oil-pressboard and pressboard-oil.

3. SIMULATION MODELS

3.1 Transmitting/receiving antenna

The dipole antenna used in the computer simulation for the source of partial discharges and the sensor of UHF signals is shown in Fig. 1. The arms of the antenna measure 60 mm x 5 mm and are made of copper.

Figure 1: Transmitting and receiving antenna model. Dipole antenna measuring 124 mm x 5 mm [13].

Fig. 2(a) shows the considered dipole antenna whose radiation is limited by a cube, side 500 mm, in order to test the overall gain of the antenna. The dipole antenna is with the central point in the position [250; 250; 250] mm. Fig. 2(b) shows the polar diagram of the total gain of a dipole UHF antenna expressed in decibels [dB], at a frequency of 1 GHz, for the position of the antenna in Fig. (2a). It can be seen from Fig. 2(b) that the transmitting dipole antenna does not emit the same radiation power in all directions.

Figure 2: (a) Dipole UHF antenna and radiation limiting cube turned approximately 45° around the z-axis in a counter-clockwise direction. (b) Polar diagram of the total gain of the antenna expressed in decibels [dB] for the position of the dipole UHF antenna in Fig. (2a) [13].

In the x-y plane where the UHF antenna is located, along the longitudinal axis of the transmitting antenna, as well as $\pm 15^\circ$ in relation to the center of the antenna, the radiation intensity is the lowest. Also, the radiation intensity along the vertical z-axis of antenna

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symmetry is weaker. The three-dimensional radiation pattern itself is more cubic than spherical. Therefore, even a receiving UHF antenna will not have equally good reception of radiated power in all directions.

3.2 Power transformer models (from the simplest to the most complex)

The model of a small three-phase energy transformer with a power of 5 MVA and a transformation ratio of 66/11 kV was considered. The dimensions of the transformer tank are: length 2300 mm, width 880 mm and height 2800 mm.

In order to compare and analyze the influence of the actual construction of the power transformer, examples of UHF signal propagation from the source of partial discharges to the receiving UHF antennas will be considered for the following cases:

- 1) for an empty transformer tank made of stainless steel 304 and filled with transformer mineral oil;
- 2) for the transformer tank made of stainless steel 304 and filled with transformer mineral oil in which the three-limb magnetic core of the transformer is located;
- 3) for a typical construction of a power transformer consisting of:
 - transformer tank made of stainless steel 304;
 - transformer insulating mineral oil;
 - three-limb, four-stage (with 7 stages) magnetic core of the power transformer;
 - three-phase low-voltage copper transformer winding;
 - three-phase high voltage copper transformer winding.

Adopted positions (center points) of receiving UHF antennas are as follows: $S_1[65; 65; 2750] \text{ mm}$, $S_2[1150; 440; 2758] \text{ mm}$, $S_3[2235; 815; 2755] \text{ mm}$, $S_4[70; 810; 2760] \text{ mm}$.

Three-phase high-voltage and low-voltage windings, due to the limited capabilities of the Ansys Electronics Desktop HFSS (High-Frequency Structure Simulator) software and the computer (i.e., processor and random-access memory), had to be simplified. The real insulation of the three-phase windings is neglected and is approximately considered to be of the dielectric strength of mineral oil because all the paper insulation of the windings is impregnated with oil, thereby reducing the dielectric strength of the insulation.

The low-voltage (LV) and high-voltage (HV) windings are made of 42 discs of the corresponding sizes. The intermediate insulation between adjacent coils of LV and HV disks in the radial direction, 1.2 mm thick, is not taken into account, it is considered to be copper. Each high-voltage disk is divided into two parts along the vertical axis with a gap of 1.2 mm, although it should be composed of four parts. The reason for this is the limited capabilities, first of all, of the random-access memory (for storing data that is simultaneously processed), and then of the processor (i.e., data processing speed) in the computer and finally the user program itself, because the model of the HV winding is multiply complicated in terms of the number of its parts. By ignoring the two gaps of 1.2 mm each, the signal attenuation is slightly higher. An opening of 1.2 mm is small for an electromagnetic wave whose wavelength in mineral oil (of dielectric constant 2.2) is equal to 20.23 cm at the wave frequency of 1 GHz. Due to wave diffraction at such a small opening, the strength of a signal beam through such an opening is dissipated in various directions relative to the opening itself, i.e., the power of that beam weakens in the direction of the shortest possible distance to the UHF sensor.

The real intermediate insulation between the higher and lower voltage windings is ignored and considered as having the dielectric strength of mineral oil, because the layers of pressboard insulation are also impregnated with oil, thus reducing the dielectric strength of the pressboard.

It was assumed that the source of partial discharges is placed at the point: $T = [2045; 600; 1250] \text{ mm}$. It is located on the front left side of the 1st pillar of the core in the upper part of the 1st phase of the winding. It is placed between the LV and HV windings, closer to the LV winding, between the 27th and 28th disks of the low-voltage winding, and behind the lower part of the 26th disk of the high-voltage winding.

The largest possible distance in the tank is 3728.86 mm, which corresponds to an electromagnetic wave delay of 18.644 ns. However, the distances between the partial discharge source and the UHF sensor are usually much shorter. The source of partial discharges is designed as a broadband pulse with a minimum frequency of 0 Hz, a maximum frequency of 1 GHz and an amplitude of 1 V.

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4. SIMULATION RESULTS

4.1. PD location equations

In order to determine the location of the source of partial discharges [1], it is necessary to use a distributed array of three or more UHF sensors to simultaneously record partial discharge signals and enable triangulation. The received UHF signals can be processed to determine the signal arrival time difference between them. The location of the source of partial discharges can then be determined from the time differences of signal arrival between UHF sensors [10,11].

For four UHF sensors, the following four equations can be written with four unknown variables [1]:

$$v_o(T_1 + T_2) = \sqrt{(x_T - x_1)^2 + (y_T - y_1)^2 + (z_T - z_1)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$v_o(T_1 + T_{21}) = \sqrt{(x_T - x_2)^2 + (y_T - y_2)^2 + (z_T - z_2)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$v_o(T_1 + T_{31}) = \sqrt{(x_T - x_3)^2 + (y_T - y_3)^2 + (z_T - z_3)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$v_o(T_1 + T_{41}) = \sqrt{(x_T - x_4)^2 + (y_T - y_4)^2 + (z_T - z_4)^2} \quad (4)$$

where:

$v_o = 20.23 \frac{cm}{ns}$ – UHF signal speed in mineral oil;

x_T, y_T, z_T – coordinates of the source T of partial discharges;

x_k, y_k, z_k – coordinates of UHF sensor k ($k = 1,2,3,4$);

T_1 – the arrival time of the partial discharge signal from the source T to the reference transmitter S_1 ;

t_{21} – difference between signal arrival times from source T to sensor S_2 and reference sensor S_1 ;

t_{31} – difference between signal arrival times from source T to sensor S_3 and reference sensor S_1 ;

t_{41} – difference between signal arrival times from source T to sensor S_4 and reference sensor S_1 .

4.2. Simulation models and results comparison

In Fig. 3, for the position of the source of partial discharges I , a simplified model of the power transformer is shown, which consists of a tank made of stainless steel 304 filled with insulating mineral oil. The recorded waveforms of the output signals of the corresponding UHF sensors are shown together in Fig. 4 in different colors.

Figure 3: Power transformer tank filled with mineral oil. (a) Front view. (b) Top view.

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Figure 4 : Displays of output signals of sensors 1-4 from Figure 3 in different colors (with green for S_1 , red for S_2 , black for S_3 and blue for S_4).

In Figure 5, for the position of the source of partial discharges T , a more complex model of the power transformer is shown, which consists of a stainless-steel tank 304 filled with insulating mineral oil and a three-limb core made of electrical steel.

Figure 5: Power transformer tank filled with mineral oil with a three-limb magnetic core. (a) Front view. (b) Top view.

The recorded signal waveforms at the output of appropriately placed UHF sensors are shown together in Figure 6 in different colors.

Figure 6: Displays of output signals of sensors 1-4 from Figure 5 in different colors (with green for S_1 , red for S_2 , black for S_3 and blue for S_4).

Figure 6 shows in the first wave packet the reduction of the amplitudes (i.e., attenuation) of the recorded signals on UHF sensors 1 and 4 by more than 1.3 times compared to the state of the signal in Figure 5 when there is no influence of the three-limb magnetic

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core. The first wave packets of signals 1 and 2 became wider than usual by about 10 ns in Figure 5 due to reflections from the core and tank.

Figure 7, for partial discharge source position T , shows a common model of a power transformer consisting of a tank of stainless steel 304 filled with insulating mineral oil, a three-limb core of electrical steel, and three-phase low and high voltage windings made of copper. The output signal waveforms of the default UHF sensors are shown together in Fig. 8 in different colors.

Figure 7: The metal tank of a power transformer with a three-limb magnetic core and three-phase copper windings, which is filled with mineral oil. (a) Front view. (b) Top view.

In Figure 8, one can see an additional drop in the amplitudes (i.e. attenuation) of the recorded signals, especially on UHF sensors 2 and 3 (more than 4 times), then on UHF sensor 1 (more than 2.8 times) and a relatively smaller drop on UHF sensor 4 (more than 1.3 times), compared to the signal condition in Figure 6 when there is no influence of the three-phase copper winding. Figures 4, 6 and 8 show how the shapes of the envelopes of the amplitudes of individual signals on UHF sensors are different, due to the effects of diffraction (i.e., deflection) around and reflection from various metal obstacles.

Table I shows the moments of the first peaks of the partial discharge signals on UHF sensors 1–4 for three examples of power transformer construction. From the results in Table I, it can be seen that the metal core almost does not affect the signal paths of partial discharges from the source to the UHF sensors D_3 and D_4 , while the signal paths to the sensors D_2 and D_1 are extended and the signals arrive later in 0.09 ns and 0.28 ns, respectively. The three-phase windings and the three-limb magnetic core affect the signal delay of (0.35–0.98) ns, depending on the position of the UHF sensor in relation to the state when the metal tank of the power transformer is empty. The largest delay is for sensor 1 and the smallest for sensor 3, 0.63 ns for sensor 4 and 0.84 ns for sensor 2.

Figure 8: Displays of output signals of sensors 1–4 from Figure 7 in different colors (with green for S_1 , red for S_2 , black for S_3 and blue for S_4).

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Table 1: Moments of the appearance of the first peaks of the partial discharge signals on sensors 1-4 for three examples of power transformer construction.

Construction	$t_1 [ns]$	$t_2 [ns]$	$t_3 [ns]$	$t_4 [ns]$
metal tank (α)	14.022	10.1623	8.9408	13.7044
+metal core (β)	14.3033	10.2517	8.8602	13.6894
+windings (γ)	14.9995	11.0034	9.2934	14.3304

Table II shows the differences in the arrival times of partial discharge signals at UHF sensors 1–4 for the theoretical case and three examples of power transformer construction.

Table 2: Calculated differences in the arrival times of partial discharge signals at sensors 1–4 for the theoretical case and three examples of power transformer construction. The sensor D_1 is taken as the reference sensor.

Construction	$dt_{21} [s]$	$dt_{31} [s]$	$dt_{41} [s]$
ideal case (ζ)	-3.856975E-09	-4.988049E-09	-2.275738E-10
metal tank (α)	-3.859711E-09	-5.081138E-09	-3.175711E-10
+metal core (β)	-4.051567E-09	-5.443014E-09	-6.138738E-10
+ windings (γ)	-3.99616E-09	-5.706145E-09	-6.691245E-10

Table III shows the mutual deviations of the differences in the arrival times of partial discharge signals at UHF sensors 1–4 and the mean value of their absolute values for the three considered simulated cases compared to the theoretical – perfect case. The sensor D_1 is taken as the reference sensor.

Table 3: Mutual deviations of the differences in the arrival times of the partial discharge signals to sensors 1–4 and the mean values of their absolute values for the considered three simulated cases compared to the ideal (theoretical) case.

Differences in arrival times	$D_2 - D_1$	$D_3 - D_1$	$D_4 - D_1$
$\Delta(dt_{\alpha\zeta}) [s]$	-2.735678E-12	-9.308934E-11	-8.999738E-11
$\Delta(dt_{\alpha\zeta sr}) [s]$		6.19408E-11	
$\Delta(dt_{\beta\zeta}) [s]$	-1.945919E-10	-4.549654E-10	-3.863E-10
$\Delta(dt_{\beta\zeta sr}) [s]$		3.452858E-10	
$\Delta(dt_{\gamma\zeta}) [s]$	-1.39185E-10	-7.180961E-10	-4.415507E-10
$\Delta(dt_{\gamma\zeta sr}) [s]$		4.329439E-10	

The mean deviation of the absolute values of the differences in the arrival times of the partial discharge signals at UHF sensors 1–4 compared to the ideal case is the largest in the 3rd simulated case, and the least in the 1st simulated case.

Table IV shows the calculated positions of the sources of partial discharges for the theoretical case and three examples of the simulated construction of the power transformer.

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Table 4: Calculate the position of the source of partial discharges for the theoretical case and three examples of simulated power transformer construction

Construction	x [m]	y [m]	z [m]
ideal case (ζ)	2.045E+00	6E-01	1.25E+00
metal tank (α)	2.059012E+00	6.654313E-01	1.209642E+00
+ metal core (β)	2.019612E+00	8.568329E-01	1.33064E+00
+ windings (γ)	2.155093E+00	9.387108E-01	1.131878E+00

Table V shows mutual deviations in the calculated positions of the sources of partial discharges and the mean value of their absolute values for the three considered simulated cases in relation to the theoretical – perfect case.

Table 5: Mutual deviations in the calculated positions of the sources of partial discharges by axes and the mean value of their absolute values for the considered three simulated cases in relation to the ideal case.

Deviations in calculated positions	x -axis	y -axis	z -axis
$\Delta d_{\alpha\zeta}$ [cm]	1.401207E+00	6.543125E+00	-4.035813E+00
$\Delta d_{\alpha\zeta sr}$ [cm]		3.993382E+00	
$\Delta d_{\beta\zeta}$ [cm]	-2.538764E+00	2.568329E+01	8.063954E+00
$\Delta d_{\beta\zeta sr}$ [cm]		1.209534E+01	
$\Delta d_{\gamma\zeta}$ [cm]	1.100931E+01	3.387108E+01	-1.181217E+01
$\Delta d_{\gamma\zeta sr}$ [cm]		1.889752E+01	

The mean deviation of the absolute values in the calculated positions of the sources of partial discharges in relation to the perfect case is the largest in the 3rd simulated case, and the least in the 1st simulated case.

5. DISCUSSION ABOUT ANOTHER CASE OF PD SOURCE LOCATION

In the article [13], the position of the source of partial discharges was considered, as in Fig. 9, which, viewed from the rear, was located on the left side of the middle limb of the electrical steel core under the yoke, in the middle part of the 2nd phase of the three-phase copper windings. It was placed between the low voltage winding and the high voltage winding, closer to the low voltage winding, opposite the 22nd disk of the low voltage winding and against the lower part of the 22nd disk of the high voltage winding. In that case, as well as for the given arrangement of the UHF sensors, the mean value of the absolute values of the deviation of the position of the source of partial discharges in relation to the actual position was the highest when the metal tank and the three-limb core of the power transformer were taken into account and was 11.3 cm. When the three-phase windings were also taken into account, the mean value of the absolute deviation of the position of the source of partial discharges was 8.2 cm. When only the metal tank of the power transformer was considered, the mean value of the absolute deviation of the position of the source of partial discharges was 1.74 cm.

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Figure 9: Complex model from article [13]: Power transformer tank filled with mineral oil with three-limb core and three-phase windings. (a) Rear view. (b) Top view [13].

In relation to the example in the article [13], in the example in this paper, the mean deviation of the absolute values of the differences in the arrival times of the partial discharge signals at the UHF sensors 1–4 compared to the ideal case is, respectively, greater by 0.183 ns and 0.357 ns in the case of influences metal core and metal core and windings together on the paths of signal propagation from the source to the UHF sensors.

It can be concluded that in the case described in article [13], the influence of the magnetic core on determining the location of the source of partial discharges was greater than the influence of the magnetic core and windings together, i.e., contrary to the example shown in this paper, although in both cases the three-phase windings additionally affected the UHF signal delays from the source of partial discharges to individual UHF sensors to a correspondingly lesser or greater extent depending on the size and number of metal obstacles. The magnitudes and ratios of the differences in the arrival times of the partial discharge signals to the UHF sensors can unexpectedly affect the magnitudes and ratios of the results obtained for the positions of the partial discharge sources when determining the influence of the magnetic core and the magnetic core and copper windings together.

6. CONCLUSION

The aim of this work was to analyze the impact of the actual construction of the power transformer on the propagation of electromagnetic UHF waves from the source of partial discharges in the electrical insulation in the tank of the power transformer from the place of their origin to the receiving UHF antennas.

With the help of simulations in HFSS, pictorial representations of the received signals are made possible, all reflections and diffractions of the signals on the way from the source to the UHF sensor are included. The disadvantage is that the source of partial discharges is not a point source, i.e., it does not radiate with the same power of radiation in all possible directions from the source.

The position of the source of partial discharges, which is seen from the front, is located on the front left side of the 1st pillar of the core in the upper part of the 1st phase of the winding. It is placed between the LV and HV windings, closer to the LV winding, between the 27th and 28th disks of the low-voltage winding, and behind the lower part of the 26th disk of the high-voltage winding.

Given the metal tank and three-limb magnetic core of the power transformer, and for the given UHF sensor arrangement, the mean absolute deviation of the position of the partial discharge source is 12.1 cm from the assumed position, because the signal path is extended, compared to when there is only an empty steel tank. When the three-phase windings are also taken into account, the mean value of the absolute values of the deviation of the position of the source of partial discharges is the highest and is 18.9 cm. When only the steel tank of the power transformer is considered, the mean value of the absolute values of the deviation of the position of the source of partial discharges is the smallest, i.e., 4 cm.

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